

Examination of the relationship between gender perception and gender roles in young adults: A case study of Karabuk province

Genç yetişkinlerde toplumsal cinsiyet algısı ile toplumsal cinsiyet rolleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi: Karabük ili örneği

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between gender perception and social gender roles in young adults in Karabük province. This descriptive correlational study was carried out with 306 students studying at Karabük University Faculty of Health Sciences between 15.12.2023-15.06.2024. The data of the study were collected using a "Personal Information Form", "Social Gender Perception Scale" and "Social Gender Roles Attitude Scale". Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 26.0 package program. The statistical significance limit was accepted as $p<0.05$. The average scores of students on the Social Gender Roles Attitude Scale were 53.71 ± 10.35 , and the average scores on the Social Gender Perception Scale were 79.75 ± 6.19 . It was observed that students' social gender perceptions and attitudes varied depending on factors such as age, gender, and family structure. In order to deepen our understanding in this field and contribute to the dissemination of egalitarian attitudes, awareness and education programs on gender equality should be examined in future research.

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ÖZ

Bu çalışma Karabük ilinde genç yetişkinlerde toplumsal cinsiyet algısı ile toplumsal cinsiyet rolleri arasındaki ilişkiyi belirlemek amacıyla yapılmıştır. Bu tanımlayıcı tipteki korelasyon çalışması, 15.12.2023- 15.06.2024 tarihleri aralığında Karabük Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesinde okuyan 306 öğrenci ile yürütülmüştür. Çalışmanın verileri "Kişisel Bilgi Formu", "Toplumsal Cinsiyet Algısı Ölçeği" ve "Toplumsal Cinsiyet Roller Tutum Ölçeği" kullanılarak toplanmıştır. İstatistiksel analizler, SPSS 26.0 paket programı kullanılarak yapılmıştır. İstatistiksel anlamlılık sınır değeri $p<0.05$ olarak kabul edildi. Öğrencilerin Toplumsal Cinsiyet Roller Tutum Ölçeği puan ortalamaları 53.71 ± 10.35 , Toplumsal Cinsiyet Algısı Ölçeği puan ortalamaları 79.75 ± 6.19 'dur. Öğrencilerin toplumsal cinsiyet algıları ve tutumlarının yaş, cinsiyet ve aile yapısı gibi faktörlere bağlı olarak değişiklik gösterdiği görülmüştür. Bu alandaki anlayışımızı derinleştirmek ve eşitlikçi tutumların yaygınlaştırılmasına katkı sağlamak amacıyla, gelecekteki araştırmalarda toplumsal cinsiyet eşitliği konusunda farkındalık ve eğitim programlarının etkisi incelenmelidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Genç Yetişkin, Toplumsal Cinsiyet, Cinsiyet Algısı, Cinsiyet Roller

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender perception in young adults is a situation related to how individuals and society perceive expectations, roles, and norms related to gender, and how they react to them. This perception plays an important role in young people's process of discovering their own sexual identities and is shaped by various factors such as social interactions, media, family, and school (Güneş & Tarhan, 2022).

Social gender inequalities have negative effects on women's lives and these effects vary from society to society (Karakaya & Özkan, 2024). Social gender includes social norms and expectations about which behaviors are

attributed to women or men within a specific culture or society. These norms can be seen in many areas such as clothing style, language use, division of labor, social roles, etc. It can be constructed in different forms due to the influence of different social factors. Therefore, while social gender is a characteristic that can vary from society to society and region to region over time, gender remains constant. Therefore, social gender roles have a changeable characteristic (Ozturk & Ay, 2020).

Gender plays a significant role in personal relationships, family, public organizations, education, social environment, in other words, in a wide range of human life (Özpuolat, 2016). Gender discrimination arises from individuals being subjected to different reactions based on whether they are male or female, rather than their abilities. This situation generally harms the entire society while negatively affecting criteria such as economy, education, health, and quality of life (Ejaz & Ara, 2011; Iqbal, 2012). Gender perception in young adults not only points to individual characteristics but also includes consequences that affect the general society. Being a woman or a man is a role that is considered quite distinct from other characteristics of the individual (Sumbas & Erdemir, 2022). Since men are generally the ones in power in the construction of gender roles in society, male characteristics are often glorified while female characteristics are devalued. Therefore, the status of women in terms of gender is determined not by their personal characteristics, but by the situations created socially. Along with differences, there are different social gender roles assigned to women and men in all societies. In this context, social expectations are developed regarding which activities and behaviors women and men can engage in, which rights they can have, and who will hold power (Güneş & Tarhan, 2022). These expectations developed according to gender norms, such as men being expected to be braver and stronger, work outside the home, while women are expected to be more emotional and in need of protection, taking care of household chores and childcare, are passed on to the new generations through socialization. Individuals prepare themselves for gender roles in every moment of their lives, but this becomes more prominent during adolescence, which is both a time of transitioning into adulthood and a time of forming sexual identity. Adolescence, one of the most important stages of human life, is a period where gender characteristics are acquired and the search for identity begins. Therefore, during this period, individuals start to feel more pressure to behave according to gender roles. Gender roles are imposed on individuals by various institutions such as family, street, school, mass media, social environment, and over time these roles are internalized (Kandemir & Nartgün, 2022). It is also one of the most basic indicators of development goals and expresses the fact that achieving gender equality is an important factor in strengthening society (Zorlutuna, 2024). In order for gender equality to spread throughout the country, it is important for policies on this issue to be produced at the local level rather than centrally (Şeker, et al., 2020). According to the Global Gender Inequality 2021 Report, Bardakçı and Oğlak (2022) evaluated some countries and stated that Türkiye is among the countries with the lowest gender equality; they mentioned that gender equality has been decreasing in all dimensions, especially in economic and political participation, since 2006 (Bardakçı & Oğlak). This study was conducted in Karabük province to determine the relationship between gender perception and gender roles in young adults.

2. METHOD

This descriptive type correlation study was conducted with 306 students studying at the Faculty of Health Sciences of Karabük University between the dates of 15.12.2023-15.06.2024. The data of the study were collected using the “Personal Information Form”, “Gender Perception Scale” and “Gender

Roles Attitude Scale". Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS 26.0 package program. The significance level was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

2.1. Objective

This study was conducted in the province of Karabük to determine the relationship between gender perception and gender roles in young adults

2.2. Type of Research

This descriptive correlational study was conducted at Karabük University Faculty of Health Sciences between 15.12.2023-15.06.2024.

2.3. Population and sample of the research:

The population of the study consists of students studying at the Faculty of Health Sciences at Karabük University. The sample of the research was determined by taking into account the correlation coefficient in the calculation. According to the statistical calculation, it was calculated that at least 138 students should be included in the research with a 95% confidence interval, based on a correlation coefficient of $r=0.30$ and a statistical analysis power of 0.80. The study was concluded with 306 participants.

2.4. Inclusion Criteria

- Do not accept to participate in the work
- To be studying at Karabük University Faculty of Health Sciences
- To be over 18 years old

2.5. Exclusion Criteria

- Leaving work halfway through without filling out surveys or scales even though you stayed to work
- Having any obstacle to communicate

2.6. Data Collection Tools

The data for the study was collected using the "Personal Information Form", "Gender Perception Scale" and "Gender Role Attitudes Scale".

2.7. Personal Information Form

In the form prepared by researchers through a literature review, there are 8 questions querying the sociodemographic characteristics of students.

2.8. Gender Perception Scale

(GPS; Altinova and Duyan, 2013). Developed to evaluate individuals' perceptions of gender roles, the GPS is a 25-item 5-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 5= strongly agree). In addition to

positive items such as “Marriage does not prevent women from working” and “A working woman can still spend enough time with her children” (10 items), the scale also includes negatively scored items such as “A woman should not work if her husband does not allow it” and “A woman without a husband is like a house without an owner” (15 items). The lowest possible score that can be obtained from the scale is 25, while the highest is 125. High scores from the scale indicate an egalitarian perception of gender roles. An exploratory factor analysis conducted to test the validity of the scale determined that it consists of a single dimension. The scale has a Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient of .87 (Altınova and Duyan, 2013). In this study, the Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be .71.

2.9. Gender Role Attitudes Scale

(GRAS) The Gender Role Attitudes Scale was developed by García-Cueto and colleagues (2015). It was adapted into Turkish by Bakioğlu and Türküm (2019). The scale consists of 20 items aimed at determining individuals’ egalitarian attitudes towards gender roles. The scale has a single-dimensional 5-point Likert type (1 = Strongly Disagree - 5 = Strongly Agree) rating. The first 2 items in the scale are directly coded, but the last 13 items are reverse-coded, and the scores from all items are added together to obtain a total score. Scores from the scale range from 15 to 75. An increase in score from the scale indicates an increase in egalitarian attitudes towards gender roles. In the original study, the Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient for the scale was calculated as .99 (Bakioğlu & Türküm, 2019). In this study, the Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient for the scale was found to be .83.

2.10. Ethical Principles

Necessary permissions were obtained from the Non-Interventional Scientific Research Ethics Committee of a university for the research (Decision No: 2023/1517 dated 06.12.2023). The permissions for the use of scales in the study were obtained from the authors of the permission letter. Before starting the research, information about the purpose of the study and how the provided information will be used was given to the students, verbal consent was obtained, and a voluntary participation form was signed. The research was conducted in accordance with the Principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

2.11. Analysis of The Data

Statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS 26.0 package program. Continuous data obtained from the study were summarized in terms of mean standard deviation, while categorical data were summarized in percentage distribution form. In the research, whether quantitative data showed a normal distribution was evaluated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. In data showing a normal distribution, Independent Samples Test was used for comparing variables consisting of two categories, One-Way ANOVA test was used for comparing variables consisting of three or more categories, and Bonferroni test was used for determining the group causing the difference. In data not showing a normal distribution, Mann-Whitney U test was used for comparing variables consisting of two categories, Kruskal-Wallis test was used for comparing variables consisting of three or more categories, and Dunn test was used for determining the group causing the difference. Spearman Correlation Analysis was used for evaluating relationships between variables. The statistical significance threshold value was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

3. PUBLICATIONS

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Table 1. The socio-demographic characteristics of students

Variable	Mean ± SD	Min-Max
Age	20.46 ± 0.14	18-31
Gender	n	%
Female	233	76.1
Male	73	23.9
Marital status		
Married	7	2.3
Single	299	97.7
Grade		
First grade	119	40.2
Second grade	127	42.9
Third grade	29	9.8
Fourth grade	21	7.1
Department		
Midwifery	116	37.9
Nursing	33	10.8
Physiotherapy and rehabilitation	151	49.3
Child development	6	2.0
Place of residence		
Homestay	54	17.6
Dormitory	190	62.1
Student house	41	13.4
Apartment	21	6.9
Economic situation		
Income equals expenses	169	55.2
Income is more than expenses	37	12.1
Income is less than expenses	100	32.7
Family type		
Elementary family	227	74.2
Extended family	69	22.5
Broken family	10	3.3

SD: Standart deviation

When the socio-demographic characteristics of the students were examined, it was found that the average age was 20.46±0.14 years, 23.9% were male, only 2.3% were married, 42.9% were studying in the second grade, approximately half were studying in the Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation department, 62.1% were staying in dormitories, 32.7% had income less than expenses, and 1/3 were in a nuclear family structure.

The average scores of the students on the Gender Role Attitudes Scale were 53.71±10.35, and the average scores on the Gender Perception Scale were 79.75±6.19.

Table 2. Comparison of students' socio-demographic characteristics with the scores of the gender role attitudes scale and the gender perception scale.

Variable	GRAS	GPS
Age	rp = -0.163 P=0.004	T=-0.151 P=0.008
Gender		
Female	56.05 ± 9.13	80.65 ± 0.39
Male	46.26 ± 10.53	76.90 ± 0.69
	T=7.698 P<0.004	Z=-4.742 P<0.001
Marital status		
Married	43.28 ± 13.68	77.33 ± 2.48
Single	53.96 ± 10.16	79.87 ± 0.36
	T=-2.726 P=0.007	Z=1.511 P=0.131
Grade		
First grade ^a	53.68 ± 9.81	79.78 ± 0.53
Second grade ^b	54.86 ± 10.18	80.00 ± 0.50
Third grade ^c	53.00 ± 10.26	79.82 ± 1.32
Fourth grade ^d	54.00 ± 11.90	78.90 ± 2.11
	F=416 P=0.742	X ² =0.097 P=0.992
Department		
Midwifery ^a	55.56 ± 8.58	80.26 ± 0.61
Nursing ^b	49.36 ± 10.10	77.64 ± 1.19
Physiotherapy and rehabilitation ^c	53.49 ± 11.08	79.79 ± 0.47
Child development ^d	47.50 ± 15.69	84.66 ± 1.45
	F=4.044 P=0.008 a>b	X ² =4.168 P=0.244
Place of residence		
Homestay ^a	51.61 ± 12.31	79.63 ± 0.82
Dormitory ^b	55.19 ± 9.46	80.85 ± 0.38
Student house ^c	51.02 ± 10.91	77.57 ± 1.04
Apartment ^d	53.71 ± 10.35	74.52 ± 2.39
	F=3.509 P=0.016	X ² =16.637 P=0.001 b>c,d
Economic situation		
Income equals expenses ^a	54.14 ± 9.78	79.68 ± 0.47
Income is more than expenses ^b	52.51 ± 10.46	80.91 ± 0.90
Income is less than expenses ^c	55.44 ± 11.27	79.68 ± 0.68
	F=0.431 P=0.651	X ² =1.329 P=0.515
Family type		
Elementary family ^a	54.27 ± 10.03	80.19 ± 0.42
Extended family ^b	50.91 ± 10.29	78.48 ± 0.75
Broken family ^c	60.50 ± 13.59	80.50 ± 1.86
	F=5.140 P=0.006	X ² =5.021 P=0.081

GRAS: Gender Role Attitudes Scale; GPS: Gender Perception Scale; F=One-Way ANOVA Test; T=Independent_Samples Test; Z= Mann-Whitney U Test, X²=Kruskal-Wallis Test

When the socio-demographic characteristics of students were compared with the average scores of the “Gender Roles Attitude Scale”, there was no significant difference between class and income status.

It was observed that there was a slightly lower level of difference in the average scores of the “Gender Roles Attitude Scale” according to the age averages of the students.

There was a statistically significant difference in the average scores of the “Gender Roles Attitude Scale” according to the gender and marital status of the students. The average scores of female students and singles were found to be higher.

It was observed that there was a statistical difference in the average scores of the “Gender Roles Attitude Scale” according to the department students were studying. In the post-hoc analysis conducted to understand which group the difference originated from, it was seen that the difference was between the midwifery department and nursing.

There were differences among groups in the multiple comparisons of the average scores of the “Gender Role Attitudes Scale” based on students’ place of residence and family type. However, it was found that there was no difference in pairwise comparisons.

When the students were compared with their socio-demographic characteristics and the average scores of the “Gender Perception Scale”, there was no significant difference in marital status, class, department they studied in, income status, and family type.

According to the average age of the students, there is a low level of negative difference in the average scores of the “Gender Perception Scale”.

There is a statistically significant difference in the average scores of the “Gender Perception Scale” according to the students’ genders. The average scores of female students were found to be higher.

In the multiple comparisons of groups in terms of students’ places of residence, there is a difference in the average scores of the “Gender Perception Scale”. In the post-hoc analysis conducted to understand which group the difference originated from, it was seen that the difference originated from students living in dormitories and apartments.

Table 3. The relationship between the average scores of the Gender Role Attitudes Scale and the Gender Perception Scale.

	Gender Perception Scale	
Gender Role Attitudes Scale	r	0.533
	p	0.001

r=Spearman’s Correlation

When comparing the average scores of students on the Social Gender Roles Attitude Scale and the Social Gender Perception Scale, a high level of positive correlation was observed between them.

4. DISCUSSION

When looking at gender discrimination, most of the studies conducted until the 1980s define men as the perpetrators of women's victimization (İlkkaracan, 2015; MacKinnin, 2020; Karakaya & Özkan, 2024). In this context, masculine or patriarchal power finds its existence through men and has the opportunity to practice its norms (Uçan, 2016). In this study conducted to determine the relationship between social gender perception and social gender roles in young adults, the average scores of students on the "Social Gender Roles Attitude Scale" were found to be 53.71 ± 10.35 , while the average scores on the "Social Gender Perception Scale" were 79.75 ± 6.19 . Overall, it is observed that students perceive and exhibit an egalitarian attitude towards gender equality.

In this study, it was observed that there is a low level of negative relationship between students' ages and their perceptions of gender and attitudes towards gender roles. In other words, as age increases, attitudes towards gender equality decrease. In Güzel's (2016) study, it was found that students' ages did not affect their attitudes towards gender roles. Gender perception is shaped by various factors, and the situation here may be due to regional differences.

In the current study, it was found that female students have higher levels of gender perceptions and attitudes towards gender roles compared to male students, and the difference between them is statistically significant. This result is similar to previous studies in the literature in terms of women having a more positive and egalitarian attitude towards gender equality compared to men (Akbulut Uzun and Özkan, 2020; Güzel, 2016, Öngen & Aytaç, 2013). Women may become more sensitive and conscious about gender discrimination or inequality experiences. Additionally, societal norms and roles may support women in being more sensitive and empathetic.

In the current study, when the scale scores were examined according to the department they were studying in, it was found that students studying in the midwifery department had higher levels of gender perceptions. In this context, we can say that the attitudes of students studying in the midwifery department towards gender equality are more egalitarian and positive compared to students studying in other departments. The reason for this could be explained by the fact that students studying in the midwifery department consist only of women.

In this study, there was no significant difference between students' class status and their attitudes towards gender roles and gender perceptions. In a study conducted by Atış (2010), no significant relationship was found between students' class level and their attitudes towards gender roles (Atış, 2010). The findings of the study are parallel to the literature.

In line with Atış's (2010) study, in this current study, no significant difference was found between students' income status and their attitudes towards gender roles and gender perceptions.

In this study, in addition to the literature, when examining students' attitudes towards family type and gender roles, and their perceptions of gender, students from broken families were found to have higher scale scores. In broken families, children often grow up with different family dynamics and various role models. This may contribute to their development of awareness about more flexible and diverse gender roles. Additionally, children raised in broken families may have to take on independence

and responsibility at an earlier age. This situation may have helped them to take a more critical look at gender roles and develop more egalitarian attitudes.

As a result, this study has shown that students' perceptions and attitudes towards gender can vary depending on factors such as age, gender, and family structure. In future research, examining the impact of awareness and education programs on gender equality can deepen our understanding in this area and contribute to the promotion of egalitarian attitudes.

5. RESULTS

The average scores of students on the Gender Role Attitudes Scale are 53.71 ± 10.35 , and the average scores on the Gender Perception Scale are 79.75 ± 6.19 . It has been observed that students' gender perceptions and attitudes vary depending on factors such as age, gender, and family structure.

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